

Quantization in the One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction Problem

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 14, 2024

The one dimensional reflection -refraction problem (which usually applies to photons, but may also apply to quantum particles with rest mass), is based on a conservation of probability equation: $1 = \text{Probability}(\text{reflect}) + \text{Probability}(\text{refract})$ ((1)). There are, however, two unknowns in this one equation and so normally one would seek a second equation, one which perhaps governs the probability. In the case of photon reflection-refraction, however, one may notice that there are three solutions: $c_1 > c_2$, $c_1 = c_2$ and $c_1 < c_2$ which all satisfy ((1)), although probability values change. For example, for $c_1 = c_2$, $\text{Probability}(\text{reflect}) = 0$. Thus, it seems that there is information underlying ((1)) which is not immediately apparent, namely the three solutions. We suggest that these represent quantization, i.e. three states, and that ((1)) is like a modulus equation for these states. In particular, if one writes ((1)) in terms of physical flux quantities and c (speeds of lights), then: $AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2$, where AA , BB and CC are the incident, reflected and refracted fluxes. AA is used etc. to show the value is positive. If $c_2 < c_1$, then $CC < AA$. As c_2 increases, it eventually becomes equal to c_1 and $BB = 0$, $AA = CC$.

The question then becomes: What happens for $c_2 > c_1$? If one sets $AA = 1$ and $c_2 = 1.5c_1$ as an example, one sees that it is possible for $CC > AA$. Thus, one may see the idea of three states appearing.

We consider linearizing (differences of squares) equation ((1)) to bring out the hidden information of quantization (i.e. we suggest that the probability equation is a modulus one) and show that for a given c_1, c_2 , there are in fact three quantized states for $B = -\text{value}, 0, \text{value}$. For given c_1, c_2 values, these are discrete states as continuity appears by changing c_1 and c_2 values. Thus, probability seems to be built-in, together with quantization if one linearizes ((1)). We have already discussed in a previous note that by linearizing, one may also bring in p, x information through $\exp(ipx)$ because $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$. The quantization, however, appears irrespective of $\exp(ipx)$ if one linearizes, but $\exp(ipx)$ gives a reason for linearizing in that one has continuity of a sum of $\exp(ipx)$ s and a second equation indicating continuity of d/dx of the function. Thus, linearization, $\exp(ipx)$ and quantization are all linked.

One Dimensional Photon Reflection-Refraction and Traditional Approach

The traditional approach to solving the one dimensional problem (1) is to match the electric field of the photon (proportional to $\cos(-wt+kx)$) for $t=0$ and $x=0$ at the n_1-n_2 interface point, where n is the index of refraction. Using A, B, C to denote the magnitude of the electric field for the incident, reflected and refracted electric field, one has:

$$A + B = C \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad Ak_1 - Bk_1 = Ck_2 \quad ((2b))$$

Using $p = \hbar k$ and $E = pc$ with E being the same for the incident, reflected and refracted rays, one obtains:

$$B/A = (c_2 - c_1) / (c_1 + c_2) \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad C/A = 2c_2 / (c_1 + c_2) \quad ((3b))$$

One does not even need the probability conservation statement ((1)) in this approach, although ((3a)) and ((3b)) do yield it.

We wish to point out that if one examines ((3a)), which represents the reflected ray, then there are three solutions:

$$c_1 < c_2 \rightarrow B = - |c_2 - c_1| / (c_1 + c_2) \quad ((4a))$$

$$c_1 = c_2 \rightarrow B = 0 \quad ((4b))$$

$$c_2 > c_1 \rightarrow B = |c_2 - c_1| / (c_1 + c_2) \quad ((4c))$$

Thus, one sees that there is quantization of the square root of the flux of the reflected ray in this problem. One has discrete values for a given c_1 and c_2 , but could have continuous values if one considered various possible c_2 , c_1 values for different problems together. This quantization suggests discrete vector projection values, we argue, for a given c_1, c_2 pair. Continuous values may be obtained from using all c_1, c_2 pairs.

Solving One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction Using the Idea of Quantization

We suggest that one may start with the conservation of probability equation ((1)) in order to emphasize the probabilistic nature of this problem, which seems to be lost in the electric field matching approach. Using physical flux values and c , the speed of light, one has:

$$AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2 \quad ((5))$$

((5)) is one equation with two unknowns and is also probabilistic. It seems as if the natural approach would be to look for a second equation governing probability at the n_1 - n_2 junction. There is an alternative math approach to obtain an answer, namely to write ((5)) as:
 $AA/c_1 - BB/c_1 = CC/c_2$ and replace $1/c_i$ with p_i . One may then break ((5)) into two equations:

$$A+B=C \text{ and } Ap_1 - Bp_1 = Cp_2 \quad ((6))$$

These may be solved to yield an answer, but there is no guarantee that this has any physical merit. There needs to be a reason to linearize and consider that probability is governed by considering equations linked to the square root of the flux.

We first note from ((5)) that if $n_1 = n_2$, then $BB=0$, so $B=0$. We suggest that BB has a leading power of $(c_1 - c_2)$.

Next, we note that if $n_2 > n_1$ (i.e. $c_2 > c_1$), then: CC could possibly be larger than AA .

Finally, if $n_2 < n_1$, i.e. $c_2 < c_1$ $AA > CC$

In other words, ((5)) is associated with three solutions, each with differing probability values. In the case of $n_1=n_2$, $A=C$ and $B=0$. In the case of $c_2 < c_1$, $A > C$ and so one might consider $A+B$, with $B < 0$, so that A decreases in magnitude as a possible situation. This line of reasoning seems to give rise to the notion of quantization of B . It could possibly have three values $|B|$, 0 , $-|B|$ for the three solutions. This idea may be tested and is exactly what the linearizing of the difference of squares yields.

In other words, the linearizing of the equation may be linked to the quantization of B which emerges to handle the three solutions, $c_1=c_2$, $c_1 < c_2$ and $c_2 > c_1$. We note that B takes on discrete values for a given c_1, c_2 pair, but if one considers all possible c_1, c_2 pairs, one has continuity. B is then like the projection of a vector. It has discrete projection values for a given c_1, c_2 pair, but using all c_1, c_2 values yields continuous results.

Thus, ((1)) seems to be an equation of magnitudes of a quantized B vector.

There is a second reason for linearizing using a difference of squares. We have discussed this in a previous note, but repeat it briefly in the next section.

The Role of p and x in One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction

The probability equation ((1)) makes no mention of x_0 , the position of the n_1 - n_2 junction, or p , momentum. This implies that the junction may be at any x and the magnitude of p (or energy) does not change the answer. Nevertheless, a priori, it seems that one should write an equation with x and p as these are physical variables. They should then ultimately drop out.

We note that if one uses the notion of probability, as in ((1)), there should be intrinsic probability in the problem. Taking the differences of squares does not show where this probability exists. We suggest that given p is a conserved quantity, i.e. it takes on the same value for all x . If there is a probability for $P_d(p,x)$, then this probability should have the same value for all x , but that would mean that it is a constant. An alternative is that it is a periodic function, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ such that the translational generator yields p multiplied by $\exp(ipx)$. This suggests that physically the probability is in $\exp(ipx)$. The reason that one does not see this probability explicitly is that $\exp(ipx)^* \exp(ipx) = 1$, where $*$ denotes the complex conjugate.

Thus, linearizing the difference of squares not only reveals a quantized B (square root of the reflected flux) as a kind of vector, but there is another two-vector $\exp(ipx)$ which accounts for the probability in the problem. All of this information is lost by only considering the magnitude equation ((1)).

Using the $\exp(ipx)$ approach, one wants this sum of functions and their first derivatives to be continuous. This leads to an expression for B which shows that it is quantized for the three solutions $c_1=c_2$, $c_1 < c_2$ and $c_1 > c_2$.

$$A \exp(ip_1 x_0) + B \exp(-ip_1 x_0) = C \exp(ip_2 x_0) \quad ((7a))$$

$$A p_1 \exp(ip_1 x_0) - B p_1 \exp(-ip_1 x_0) = C p_2 \exp(ip_2 x_0) \quad ((7b))$$

One may multiply ((7a)) by the complex conjugate of ((7b)) to obtain ((1)) using $x_0=0$, which may always be chosen by shifting the ruler.

Thus, the quantization of B seems to be linked to $\exp(ipx)$ and discrete B values appear for a given c_1, c_2 pair.

Particle with a Rest Mass

Similar ideas hold for a particle with rest mass, because one may have a similar reflection-refraction problem by having two regions, one with a constant potential V_1 and the other with V_2 . Energy is again the same for incident, reflected and refracted $\exp(ipx)$ s. One may again write ((7a)) and ((7b)) to describe the problem and there is again quantization of B for the reflected ray for the cases: $V_1=V_2$, $V_1<V_2$ and $V_1>V_2$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is possible to obtain the probability to reflect and refract by linearizing a probability conservation equation, written in terms of flux and speed of light for one dimensional photon reflection-refraction. The results obtained match those of the continuity of the electric field and its first derivative for a photon approach. A priori, however, one may ask: Why is this the case? There should be a reason for linearizing a difference of squares.

We suggest that there seem to be two reasons. One reason we have discussed in a previous note, namely that x and p should appear a priori, even if they later drop out. In fact, it seems that it is a function of p, x which accounts for the probability in the problem, not an external probability. In other words, one may impose continuity of a sum of $\exp(ipx)$ terms and their derivatives, i.e. ((7a)), ((7b)).

In this note, however, we point out a different feature, namely the quantization of B, the square root of the reflected flux. We note that there are three solutions, one for $c_1=c_2$, $c_1>c_2$ and $c_1<c_2$. For $c_1=c_2$, $B=0$. We suggest that B has a role to play in the other two cases. In other words, it seems as if B is like a discrete set of vector projections, one for each solution. In such a case, a probability statement ((1)) could represent a magnitude equation. This, we suggest, would justify linearizing the probability equation. If one tests this idea, one does indeed find that B is quantized as $|B|$, 0 , $-|B|$. The discrete values hold for a given c_1, c_2 pair, but one may obtain continuity by considering all possible c_1, c_2 pairs. Thus, there seems to be a hidden vector projection B in the problem, with projections related to the three solutions. This information is lost if one does linearize. This same linearization, however, is linked to $\exp(ipx)$, so quantization is also linked to $\exp(ipx)$. These ideas may be extended to a particle with rest mass.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change